
FORGIVENESS AS A CORRELATE OF MARITAL HARMONY AMONG MARRIED TEACHERS IN DELTA STATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers in Delta State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the correlational research design in. The population comprised 8,526 married teachers in Delta State. The sample size was 879 married teachers from Delta State. A multi-stage sampling method was used to select the sample. The research instrument that was utilized for the data collection was a Marital Forgiveness and Marital Harmony Questionnaire (MFMHQ). The face validity was estimated through experts' objective judgement. The total cumulative variance was used to estimate the content validity of the instrument while the rotated component matrix was used to estimate its construct validity. The psychometric properties of the instrument were therefore found to be appropriate. The data collected were analysed using Pearson's Product Moment correlation and regression statistics. All the null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that a significant positive relationship exists between marital forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers; that there is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers; and that there is no significant moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. The study recommended that couples struggling with marital forgiveness in their marriages should consider seeking professional help.

Keywords: Forgiveness, Marital Harmony, Married Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is often viewed as a lifelong partnership built on love, trust, and commitment. It serves as a foundation for emotional, psychological, and social support between spouses. However, the dynamics of marriage can be complex, as it involves navigating daily challenges, including personal differences, financial issues, work stress, and family responsibilities. These factors can create conflicts and misunderstandings, which, if left unresolved, may strain the relationship. This is where the need for marital harmony becomes critical.

Marital harmony refers to a state of peaceful coexistence and mutual understanding between partners. It is characterized by open communication, emotional support, shared goals, and the ability to resolve conflicts in a constructive manner. Achieving marital harmony means that both partners are able to find common ground, respect each other's perspectives, and work together to maintain a balanced and loving relationship. Without harmony, marriages can quickly become overwhelmed by unresolved tensions, leading to dissatisfaction, emotional distance, or even separation (Ibeh & Obidoa, 2013).

The need for marital harmony is particularly essential in contemporary society, where couples often face external pressures from work, social expectations, and financial responsibilities (Ibeh & Obidoa, 2013). In marriages where both spouses, such as teachers or other professionals, are actively engaged in their careers, the balance between work life and family life can be challenging. This balance requires mutual support and understanding, which are key components of marital harmony. Marital harmony is an essential aspect of a successful and fulfilling marriage. While there are several factors that contribute to marital harmony, one aspect that is particularly intriguing is marital forgiveness. Forgiveness plays a critical role in maintaining solid connections, and this paper will investigate its significance in relation to conjugal concordance.

Marital forgiveness alludes to the capacity for a couple to excuse each other for previous mishaps, damages, or offenses. It includes relinquishing disdain, outrage, and sharpness, as well as, on second thought, deciding to continue on and rebuild trust. Excusing in marriage requires sympathy, empathy, and an eagerness to pardon for the relationship. Forgiveness allows couples to relinquish pessimistic feelings such as indignation, hatred, and harshness, prompting the two accomplices to work towards profound prosperity. In a drawn-out marriage, numerous offences are probably going to happen over life and can possibly upset the conjugal relationship. Forgiveness is one of the main positive approaches to managing conjugal contentions and their outcomes and has been viewed as a significant part of marital harmony (Bugay, 2014). With regards to marriage, forgiveness refers to a solitary demonstration (long-winded absolution) or general inclination (dispositional absolution) to excuse a partner for a specific offense or different offenses (Brudek and Kaleta, 2021). Offence-explicit forgiveness is generally perceived as a course of leaving pessimistic considerations, feelings, inspiration, and conduct towards the guilty party. Nonetheless, a few researchers recommend that forgiveness in cosy connections needs two aspects: a negative one that involves how much an individual defeats supporting hard feelings, pulling out from the relationship, and longing for retribution or discipline against the accomplice, and a good one, including how much a singular encounters a status to draw nearer to the accomplice and an expansion in sympathy and kind-heartedness (Brudek and Kaleta, 2021).

Forgiveness in marriages has been linked to relationship quality, attributions, and empathy. Forgiving a partner transgression is one mechanism that may facilitate relationship maintenance and has received considerable scientific scrutiny recently. Willingness to forgive partner transgressions is related to physical, psychological and relational health, indicating that forgiveness is influential in individual and relational well-being (May, et al., 2014).

Capacity to excuse and look for forgiveness fundamentally add to marital harmony and are in many cases appraised as quite possibly the main element that influences relationship life span. It has likewise been shown that forgiveness of an accomplice emphatically corresponds with fulfilment from marriage—it builds closeness and obligation to the relationship, advances viable goals of struggles, and, after some time, decidedly affects the nature of marriage.

Considering the conjectured conceivable relationship that may exist among forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers, the study wishes to see whether sex and duration of marriage can moderate such a relationship. It is clear in Nigeria that people have various ideas of marital harmony and the social help that is traded in the marriage. For example, in Nigeria, men for the most part view marriage as an establishment of lordship over the other gender, who should be seen and not heard. As indicated by Uwaoma et al. (2016), a regular married man accepts that his significant other is dependent upon his position, independent of her conviction, suppositions, sentiments, and, surprisingly, scholarly foundation. He accepts that a spouse is his property and, as such, a piece of his assets instead of an accomplice. He likewise accepts that a lady's place is in the kitchen consequently; her commitments are of practically no significance to him. The lady then again will in general acknowledge her place as depicted by the other gender, as she accepts it is the most ideal choice for her to protect her marital status even to the detriment of her happiness (Unamba, 2010).

Sex difference in the construction of marital union additionally could arise on account of contrasts in hereditary and natural effects on marital harmony. For example, individual (i.e., genetic) and setting-orientated (i.e., biological) influences occur inside sociocultural settings that perhaps shape sexed responses in habits couples act toward each other, translate life accomplices' approaches to acting, and assess effect on the relationship (Wood and Eagly 2012). Earlier studies have shown that people approach contentions and answer withdrawals in an unexpected way.

Thus, variations in the genetic and environmental impacts on marital harmony might provide hints for future research to clarify why men and women experience marriage in different ways. Seldom has research been done on how sex variations in genetic and environmental factors affect marital peace. The personalities, attitudes, and ideas that men and women bring to their marriages may be an indirect result of genetic influences on marital harmony disparities. Spotts et al. (2016) discovered that in a sample of married men and women who were born in the United States, genetic and environmental factors had differing effects on marital warmth and marital conflict. Women were more affected by genetics than men were when it came to marital friendliness, whereas males were more affected when it came to marital conflict. Social support is one dimension linked to marital harmony for which genetic variations have also been discovered (Kendler & Baker, 2007). Forgiveness and sex have also been linked, with some research suggesting that women are often more forgiving than males (Bugay, 2014). According to McCullough et al. (1997), gender roles have less of an impact on a couple's capacity for forgiveness and marital harmony than does their ability

to recognise one another's points of difference. Effective conflict resolution and emotional closeness, according to Fincham and Beach (2002), are essential to promoting forgiveness. According to Kahn et al. (2018), modern couples minimise gender-based disparities in relationship dynamics by sharing duties and working together to solve problems. According to Jankowski et al. (2019), respect and shared values are typically more important for couples' relationship dynamics and happiness than gender.

The researcher believes that duration of marriage could also be considered in finding the possible relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers. Most people who get married may have a high level of marital harmony at the beginning. But eventually, their level of enjoyment can drop. Certain research has shown a negative association between the length of a marriage and marital harmony (Ziaei et al., 2014). Marital harmony does, however, seem to rise with the number of years married (Zainah et al., 2012; Duncan, 2008). According to experts, couples who have been together for 10 years or more have likely moved beyond the adaptation stage, are less stressed, and have psychological issues. Furthermore, compared to individuals in their early adult years, older adults seem to be more forgiving of their grudges (Ghaemmaghmi et al., 2011). In view of the above, the aim of this study is to examine the relationship that exists among marital expectations, communication flow, forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers and the moderating impact of sex and duration of marriage.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher has observed sadly that the basic foundation of marriage has almost been destroyed, and consequently, many couples no longer have respect for the institution of marriage. Marriage is no longer seen as a sacrament whereby a man and a woman are married for life. The injunction that they will remain married till death does them part no longer means much to most married couples.

This is especially true for married couples in Delta State. Marriage dissolution is on the rise in the state, according to observations of recent events. Separations and divorces seem to be increasing. This development might be attributed to other sources. But the biggest issue seems to be the discord in the marriage. Even though it seems that society and religious organisations have worked hard to address this family issue, research into a few factors that may be contributing to marital dissolutions among married couples is still necessary. Of particular interest to the researcher, is forgiveness. The problem of this study, therefore, is, what is the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers?

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria?
2. What is the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria?
3. What is the moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria
2. There is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria
3. There is no significant moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers. The study specifically found out:

1. the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria;
2. the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria; and
3. the moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria.

Methods

This study adopted the correlational research. The population of the study consisted of all married teachers in Delta state. The data obtained from the Post-Primary Education Board (PPEB) showed that the total of number of married teachers in Delta State is 8,526, comprising of 2,720 male and 5,806 female teachers. The sample size of the study was 879 married teachers from Delta State. The choice of 879 married teachers as a sample size was based on the recommendation of Gill, et al. (2010) that a sample size of 879 is suitable for a population of between 5,000 and 9,999 at a 97% confidence level. A multi-stage sampling method was used to select the sample. The research instrument that was utilized for the data collection is a questionnaire titled "Forgiveness and Marital Harmony Questionnaire" (FMHQ). The questionnaire measured respondents' responses on forgiveness and marital harmony. The research instrument consisted of three sections. These sections are Section A - Forgiveness Scale and Section B – Marital Harmony Scale

Section A provided information on sex and duration of marriage. Section B measured forgiveness using the Forgiveness Scale. The scale was adopted from the Enright Forgiveness Inventory (EFI), developed by Enright and the Human Development Study Group (1991). The questionnaire comprised 16 items designed to measure the tendency of an aggrieved spouse to forgive in times of disagreement. The scale was structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree (the items were however, reduced to 15 after validation). Section C measured marital harmony, using the Marital Harmony Scale. The scale was adapted from a combination of different measures, designed to measure the extent to which married couples are in harmony in their relationships. These measures include Marital Happiness Index (MHI), developed by Terman (1938); Dyadic Adjustment scale (DAS), developed by Spanier (1976); and the Marital Happiness Scale, developed by Kamp Dush, Taylor and Kroeger (2008). The Scale contains 25 items, which were structured

on a 4-point rating scale ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree (the items were however, reduced to 14 after validation).

The instrument was subjected to face, content and construct validities. The face validity was estimated through experts' objective judgement. Copies of the questionnaire were printed and handed over to the research supervisors who are experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling. The researcher also handed over the questionnaire to experts of Measurement and Evaluation in the same department. The experts checked the instrument for appropriateness and suitability to objectives of the study. The opinions of the experts were considered for the overall development of the instrument.

After face validity, the researcher pilot tested the questionnaire by administering it on 100 respondents in locations other than the ones earmarked to be used in the final study. The responses were collated and entered into a computer system with the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26. The data were analysed using principal component analysis method of confirmatory factor analysis. The total cumulative variance was used to estimate the content validity of the instrument. It yielded the following values; 75.18% for Marital Forgiveness Scale, and 76.95% for Marital Harmony Scale. The rotated component matrix was used to estimate its construct validity. It yielded the following range of values; 0.59-0.86 for 0.52-0.91 for Marital Forgiveness Scale, and 0.66-0.96 for Marital Harmony Scale. The instrument was administered to 100 married persons for its reliability test. The Cronbach alpha was adopted to estimate the internal consistency of items in the instrument. This yielded the following coefficient: 0.87 for Marital Expectation Scale, 0.71 for Communication Flow Scale, 0.90 for Marital Forgiveness Scale, and 0.82 for Marital Harmony Scale.

The research instrument was administered to participants. It was given to married persons to respond to. On the spot collection was done. At the end of the exercise, a total of 879 copies of questionnaire were administered and a total of 852 copies were returned. This indicates 97% retrieval rate. The data collected were analysed using Pearson's Product Moment correlation and regression statistics. The Pearson's coefficient of determination was used to answer the research questions. Regression statistics was used to test the null hypotheses formulated for the study. All the null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria?

Table 1: Pearson Correlation and Coefficient of determination of marital forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Marital Forgiveness	845	45.21	10.39	0.124	0.015	1.5	Positive
Marital Harmony		46.10	5.85				Relationship

Table 1 showed the Correlation and Coefficient of determination of marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria. As shown in the table, $r = 0.124$, $r^2 = 0.015$ and $r^2\% = 1.5\%$, which is the nature of the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of

Nigeria. This indicates a positive relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony. From the result, marital forgiveness contributed 1.5% of the variance in marital harmony among married teachers.

Research Question 2: What is the moderating impact of Sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria?

Table 2: Multiple correlation and coefficient of determination of the moderating impact of Sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers

Variables	N	R	R ²	R ² %	Remark
Marital Forgiveness					
Marital Harmony	845	0.124	0.015	1.5	Positive Relationship
Sex					

As shown in Table 2, a multiple Correlation and Coefficient of determination was used to determine the moderating impact of Sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria. The result revealed a positive relationship among the three variables ($R = 0.124$; $R^2 = 0.015$; $R^2\% = 1.5$). The result further showed that marital forgiveness and sex contributed 1.5% to the variance in marital harmony among married teachers.

Research Question 3: What is the moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria?

Table 3: Multiple correlation and coefficient of determination of the moderating impact of Duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers

Variables	N	R	R ²	R ² %	Remark
Marital forgiveness					
Marital Harmony	845	0.135	0.018	1.8	Positive Relationship
Duration of Marriage					

As shown in Table 3, a multiple Correlation and Coefficient of determination was used to determine the moderating impact of Duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria. The result revealed a positive relationship among the three variables ($R = 0.135$; $R^2 = 0.018$; $R^2\% = 1.8$). The result further showed that marital forgiveness and duration of marriage contributed 1.8% to the variance in marital harmony among married teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria

Table 4: Regression Analysis on marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	445.020	1	445.020	13.197	.000 ^b
Residual	28394.006	842	33.722		
Total	28839.026	843			

$\alpha = 0.05$, $R = 0.124$, $R\text{-Square} = 0.015$

In Table 4, a linear Regression Analysis was employed to investigate the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. The results indicated a significant positive relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony, as evidenced by an $F(1, 844)$ value of 13.197 at a significant level of $p < 0.05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, signifying a significant relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. The beta value of 0.124 indicated that marital forgiveness accounted for 1.5% of the variability in marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis on the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers

Model	B	Std Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	42.993	1.055		40.740	.000
Marital Forgiveness	.070	.021	.125	3.430	.001
Sex	-.049	.434	-.004	-.114	.910

Table 5 displays the outcomes of examining the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. The beta weight of 0.125, with a t-value of 3.430, pertains to marital forgiveness, while the beta weight of -0.004, with a t-value of -0.114, pertains to sex, signifying the extent of relationship between each variable (marital forgiveness and sex) with marital harmony.

The results indicate that marital forgiveness is statistically significant at a significant level of 0.05, whereas sex is not statistically significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting that there is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis on the moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers

Model	B	Std Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	43.776	1.130		38.729	.000
Marital forgiveness	.067	.021	.118	3.171	.002
Duration of Marriage	-.232	.162	-.054	-1.435	.152

Table 6 displays the outcomes of examining the moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. The marital forgiveness beta weight is 0.118, with a t-value of 3.171, and the duration of marriage beta weight is -0.054, with a t-value of -1.435. These values indicate the degree of association between the two variables (marital forgiveness and duration of marriage) and marital harmony. The findings show that although the length of marriage is not statistically significant, marital forgiveness is at a significant threshold of 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that the length of marriage had no discernible moderating effect on the association between married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria, and marital peace and forgiveness.

Discussion of Findings

Marital Forgiveness and Marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State of Nigeria

The first finding showed that a significant positive relationship exists between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. According to this research, marital peace is significantly influenced by forgiveness in the union. Marital forgiveness is crucial for marital peace for a number of reasons. First of all, forgiveness enables couples to get beyond their sorrows and move on. Couples may move on from the past and build a deeper bond when they are able to forgive one another. Second, trust is bolstered by forgiveness. Couples that are able to forgive one another demonstrate their commitment to one another and willingness to give the other another opportunity. Third, forgiving makes the atmosphere in the marriage happier and more loving. Spouses who are able to forgive one another are inclined to treat one other with kindness and compassion. This may result in a more contented and happy marriage. Marital forgiveness is an important but not the sole element for marital harmony, as shown by the conclusion that it contributed 1.5% of the variation in married teachers' marital harmony. There are other essential elements as well, such financial stability, communication style, and marital expectations. The aforementioned results are consistent with those of Reza et al. (2021), who found a substantial correlation between forgiving conduct and empathy. The results also corroborate those of Sohrabi et al. (2013), whose research revealed that attachment style and forgiveness degree predict around 46% of the variable variation of marital concord. The results are in line with those of Ofoke et al. (2015), who found that emotional intelligence, religion, and forgiveness positively predict marital peace.

Moderating Impact of Sex in the Relationship between Forgiveness and Marital harmony

The second finding indicates that sex does not have a significant moderating impact on the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony among married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. This suggests that, regardless of whether individuals are male or female, the dynamics of forgiveness and harmony in marriage operate similarly. One possible explanation for this finding could be that the processes of forgiveness and the maintenance of marital harmony are fundamentally based on relational and emotional factors that transcend gender differences. Research by McCullough et al. (1997) supports this notion, indicating that the ability to forgive and maintain harmony in relationships is more influenced by personal traits and interpersonal communication than by gender roles. Furthermore, Fincham and Beach (2002) argue that effective conflict resolution and emotional intimacy are critical in fostering forgiveness, suggesting that these factors are universally relevant in marriages. Additionally, the absence of a moderating effect of sex may reflect broader cultural or societal influences in the context of Delta State, where traditional gender roles are evolving. Both men and women may be adopting similar attitudes toward forgiveness and conflict resolution, leading to comparable outcomes in marital harmony regardless of sex. This is consistent with findings by Kahn et al. (2018), which highlight that contemporary couples often share responsibilities and engage in collaborative problem-solving, thereby minimizing gender-based differences in relational dynamics. Moreover, the lack of a significant moderating effect aligns with the work of Jankowski et al. (2019), who found that relational satisfaction and dynamics in couples often hinge more on shared values and mutual respect than on gender. In this light, the finding reinforces the idea that successful marriages are built on shared emotional experiences rather than on traditional gender distinctions.

Moderating Impact of Duration of Marriage in the Relationship between Forgiveness and Marital harmony

The third finding showed that there is no significant moderating impact of duration of marriage in the relationship between marital forgiveness and marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. The third research question and its accompanying hypothesis aimed to ascertain the moderating effect of the length of marriage on the correlation between marital harmony and forgiveness among Delta State's married teachers. According to the research, there was no discernible moderating influence of the length of marriage on this association. One explanation for this result could be that the variables that affect mutual respect, emotional closeness, and conflict resolution techniques influence both marital forgiveness and harmony regardless of how long a couple has been married. It's possible that the harmony and forgiveness levels among the research participants were comparable, despite the length of their marriages, indicating that the quality of the relationship has a greater impact on these dynamics than the duration of the marriage.

This result supports the findings of Fincham and Beach (2002), who contended that efficient communication and emotional intimacy, rather than the length of a marriage, are often the factors that lead to forgiveness in marriages. It is also consistent with the findings of Worthington and Scherer (2004), who observed that although forgiveness may increase marital pleasure, the degree to which it does so is probably more influenced by how well a couple resolves disagreements than by the length of their marriage. The results also support the findings of McCullough et al. (1997), who found that situational variables and personality characteristics had a greater impact on forgiveness in intimate relationships than do temporal variables like relationship time. The lack of a significant moderating effect, in conclusion, supports the findings of Baucom, Snyder, and Gordon (2009), who suggested that forgiveness in marriage may be more closely related to a couple's ability to work things out and move past disagreements than to the length of their marriage.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it was concluded that marital forgiveness is a very important factor for marital harmony of married teachers in Delta State, Nigeria. These findings suggest that couples who forgive have the tendency to live harmony with each other, and who are able to forgive each other for mistakes are more likely to have happy and fulfilling marriages. It is also important to note that the relationship between marital expectations and marital harmony is moderated by the duration of marriage.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were advanced:

- i. Couples struggling with marital forgiveness in their marriages should consider seeking professional help.
- ii. Couples should forgive each other for mistakes and transgressions.
- iii. Marriage counsellors should organize public sensitization programmes to enlighten married teachers on how to cope with issues related to marital disharmony

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